

THE TAUTOMERISM OF NITROUS ACID.

BY H. KRALL.

A tautomeric constitution for nitrous acid :

explains many otherwise obscure observations. The *hydroxy* form predominates. Mineral acids favour the *nitro* form and the change proceeds rapidly; the reverse change is slow. It is the *nitro* form which acts as an oxidising agent.

Laar (*Ber.*, 1885, **13**, 655) suggested the tautomerism of nitrous acid and in view of the importance of this reagent, the re-examination of the subject seems overdue.

Nitrous acid has been extensively used by Werner in his investigations of carbamide and thiocarbamide (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, **111**, 863; 1912, **101**, 2180) on the assumptions that (i) nitrous acid reacts quantitatively with an amino group involving nitrogen, and (ii) if any alteration in the experimental conditions (usually p_{H}) alters the amount of nitrogen involved, this may be taken both as an indication and as a measure of tautomeric change in the substance under examination. The same rationale has been used by the present author in the study of phenylthiocarbamide and its homologues (Krall *et al.*, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 640; 1937, **14**, 478; 1938, **15**, 217).

If nitrous acid itself is tautomeric and if, as appears to be the case, its equilibrium is displaced by change of p_{H} , this does not necessarily invalidate the inferences previously drawn, but clearly imposes caution owing to the recognition of an unsuspected factor:

Now if nitrous acid is not tautomeric, its spontaneous decomposition must occur according to some such process as

But to the present author it appears axiomatic that under conditions of molecular homogeneity (*e.g.* in the absence of a 'reagent') one molecule can break down in only one way; and whenever a *compound* breaks down in two different ways simultaneously this fact indicates the existence of two different *molecules*, *i.e.* tautomerism. This principle is not sufficiently widely

recognised. There is no support for the supposition that some molecules of HONO split up at one bond and some at the other in the same aqueous solution, *i.e.* under identical conditions. If, however, a mobility, already made familiar by the chemistry of the oximes, is postulated, the spontaneous decomposition can be formulated quite rationally:

Taylor (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 1099, 1897) examined the action of nitrous acid on ammonia, methylamine and amino-acids by physical methods, and found the reaction to be of the third order involving two molecules of nitrous acid of which only one interacted, and that mineral acids retarded the reaction. No mechanism was suggested for these remarkable results. The merely statistical results of physical chemistry may be open to various chemical interpretations, and the fact that a second equivalent of nitrous acid is required but takes no part in the change and cannot be replaced by a mineral acid is challenging. But if nitrous acid is tautomeric, all the known facts are reconciled, for the amino group (or rather its cation, *vide infra*) interacts with the *hydroxy* form and this involves the presence of the inert *nitro* form. This assumes that the attainment of equilibrium between the tautomers is slow compared with the other reaction, an assumption which receives confirmation from the frequent observation with thiocarbamides that when treated with nitrous acid there is first a brisk evolution of gas and then a period of slower evolution that may last for hours.

When nitrous acid functions as an oxidising agent it is probably the *nitro* tautomer that oxidises, and this would agree with our general observation of its action on thiocarbamides where the presence of mineral acids favours oxidation (Krall *et al.*, *loc. cit.*).

If we represent the action of nitrous acid on amines thus:

remembering that it is 'b' and not 'a' which interacts, we see that the addition of a stronger acid will do two things; it will partially replace 'a' which will then join the equilibrium 'b' \rightleftharpoons 'c' and it will also favour 'c' at the expense of 'b'. If the former displacement is greater than the second, the amount of HO·NO will be increased and the reaction accelerated by mineral acids; if the contrary, the reaction will be retarded; as the latter is Taylor's inference, we are justified in the quantitative inference that

the displacement $\text{HO}\cdot\text{NO} \rightarrow \text{H}\cdot\text{NO}_2$ is more strongly influenced by mineral acids than the displacement

The main difference between Taylor's results for the amino-acids and for methylamine is that while the reaction is termolecular in both cases, it does not set in at all with methylamine with only one equivalent of nitrous acid; but this is not surprising, for methylamine is a strong enough base to hold up a whole equivalent; there *need* only be enough 'salt formation' to provide the cation $\text{R}\cdot\text{NH}_3$, since it is this which actually interacts (Werner, *loc. cit.*, p. 865; Taylor, *loc. cit.*, p. 1905). The stability of the salts of methylamine no doubt greatly facilitates investigation by physical methods, but the results cannot be regarded as typical since amines are usually weak bases; results obtained with amino-acids are clearly better worth close investigation.

As Taylor's procedure was directed to measuring the rates rather than the results of reaction, his experiments are not comparable with those obtained in the nitrometer in the study of carbamides and thiocarbamides. In the following experiments we followed the latter method (*loc. cit.*) using milli-molar quantities of the reagents named and allowing the reactions to proceed for 24 hours. The total quantity of gas obtainable if the reaction went to completion would be 11 c.c. Brown oxides of nitrogen are not obtained as they are reduced by the mercury to nitric oxide.

	N_2 .	NO and NO_2 .
I. Ammonium nitrite gave 1.16 c.c. solely N_2 ,	say 1	0
II. Sodium nitrite and acetic acid gave 0.8 c.c. solely NO ,	0	1
III. Sodium nitrite and hydrochloric acid gave 6.6 c.c. solely NO ,	0	7
IV. Ammonium nitrite and acetic acid gave 7.1 c.c. in which NO is 13%,	6	1
V. Ammonium nitrite and hydrochloric acid gave 7.2 c.c. in which NO is 71%,	2	5

In IV and V the acids will compete for the base, so we may write:

the predominant components being underlined. Now (from I) ammonium nitrite alone only gave 1 c.c. of nitrogen, therefore the left side of IV must have given not more than 1 c.c. but the whole of IV gave 6 c.c., therefore

the *right* side (progressively replenished, of course) gave 5 c.c. ; in other words it is nitrous acid and the cation which interact as maintained by both Werner and Taylor. Probably the decomposition of ammonium nitrite alone takes place in the same way, the nitrous acid being furnished by hydrolysis

Further, if IV is compared with V it will be evident that since the right side of V represents the predominant condition it should be expected to give more than 5 c.c. but in fact the whole change only furnishes 2 c.c. That is to say that although the right side of V provides more of the ammonium anion and also more free nitrous acid than IV, the nitrogen produced is less ; evidently the nitrous acid is not available to such an extent in V and this is at once explained if it is tautomeric and if mineral acids favour the form $\text{H}'\text{NO}_2$. Indeed the figures for IV, and V, in themselves at once suggest some change of constitution in the reactants rather than a p_a effect of acceleration or retardation.

The alternative view that the text-book decomposition of nitrous acid as retarded by mineral acids sufficiently explains these facts can no longer be accepted for the following reasons : (i) As already pointed out the usual formulation of the decomposition of nitrous acid is itself very hard to accept, and is only one degree less absurd than the view that dehydration takes place even in dilute solution :

(ii) It is not clear why hydrogen ions should influence any of these changes, whereas on the tautomeric hypothesis, an effect of hydrogen ions would be anticipated and is in fact observed. (iii) The difference between II and III (noting that excess of acid was not used, but only one equivalent, sufficient to liberate the nitrous acid) cannot be due to any *catalytic* effect of hydrogen ions, but indicates clearly that the nitrous acid liberated in one case is not the same as that liberated in the other ; if the 'decomposition' of nitrous acid is an interaction between two tautomers it will be greatest when they are present in equal amounts, and the decomposition will, therefore, be 'accelerated' or 'retarded' by mineral acids according to the conditions of experiment.

To ascertain the equilibrium between the tautomers would necessitate careful and perhaps difficult dynamic experiments, but a guess may be hazarded that in the absence of acids, stronger than itself, there is less than

10% of the form $\text{H}\cdot\text{NO}_2$ (II and IV), and that when liberated by one equivalent of hydrochloric acid under above conditions this form increases to some 30% of the whole.

The above view of nitrous acid affords a simple explanation of the results obtained by Macmillan and Reade (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2863) and Donald and Reade (*ibid.*, 1935, 53) who found that certain aromatic tertiary amines gave simultaneously (a) nitro compounds and (b) nitrosoamines and that high temperatures and high acidity favoured (a), whereas the contrary conditions favoured (b). There could hardly be clearer proof of the views expressed above.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Molar solutions of ammonium chloride, sodium nitrite, hydrochloric acid and acetic acid, all of A. R. quality were prepared in distilled water. All the experiments were carried out in a Lunge nitrometer in the same way as urea and thiocarbamide experiments (*loc. cit.*). The reaction mixture was in all cases 3 c. c. and was not shaken. The volume of gas was noted after 24 hours. Concordant results were obtained.

I. *Decomposition of aqueous ammonium nitrite.*—Sodium nitrite ($\frac{1}{2}$ c. c.) and ammonium chloride ($\frac{1}{2}$ c. c.) were introduced and washed down with water (2 c. c.). Gas evolved 1.4 c. c. at 31° and 736 mm. or 1.16 c. c. at N.T.P. and was wholly nitrogen.

II. *Decomposition of nitrous acid liberated by one equivalent of acetic acid.*—Sodium nitrite ($\frac{1}{2}$ c. c.) was introduced and washed down with water ($\frac{1}{2}$ c. c.); acetic acid was then added ($\frac{1}{2}$ c. c.) and washed down with water (1 c. c.). Only minute bubbles were observed and the mercury was not appreciably tarnished. Gas evolved 1 c. c. at 29° and 735 mm. or 0.8 c. c. at N.T.P. and was wholly nitric oxide.

III. *Decomposition of nitrous acid liberated by one equivalent of hydrochloric acid.*—As in II, but using hydrochloric acid ($\frac{1}{2}$ c. c.) instead of acetic acid. The evolution of gas was more rapid than in II, and measured 7.9 c. c. at 30° and 735 mm. or 6.6 c. c. at N.T.P. and was wholly nitric oxide. Brown oxides of nitrogen were not obtained in this or any other case as they were reduced by the mercury which became tarnished.

IV. *Decomposition of ammonium nitrite in the presence of one equivalent of acetic acid.*—Sodium nitrite ($\frac{1}{2}$ c. c.) and ammonium chloride

($\frac{1}{2}$ c. c.) were introduced and the cup washed down with water ($\frac{1}{2}$ c. c.). Acetic acid ($\frac{1}{2}$ c. c.) was then added and washed down with water (1 c. c.). The reaction was slow. Gas evolved 8.7 c. c. at 33° and 736 mm. or 7.1 c. c. at N.T.P. and contained nitric oxide 13% and nitrogen 87%.

V. *Decomposition of ammonium nitrite in the presence of one equivalent of hydrochloric acid.*—As in IV, but using hydrochloric acid ($\frac{1}{2}$ c. c.) instead of acetic acid. The reaction was rapid at first and slow later; the mercury was tarnished. Gas evolved 8.8 c. c. at 32° and 736 mm. or 7.2 c. c. at N.T.P. and contained nitric oxide 71% and nitrogen 29%.

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AGRA COLLEGE,
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